

Simulating the tidal disruption of the Hyades cluster stellar streams

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Abstract

Previous studies have used n-body simulations to model the Hyades open cluster in an attempt to determine the initial conditions of the progenitor globular cluster at the time of its formation. In this thesis, we perform new simulation of the evolution of the Hyades using up-to-date information of its stream members using GAIA data release 2 (GAIA DR2) data. Our simulations were performed in a gravitational background potential with a co-evolving halo potential based in cosmological simulations and a static disk potential, using NBODY6++ code to compute the interactions between stars in the cluster and the gravitational background. This study produced several simulations of stellar streams with similar morphology to the observed Hyades cluster. We have performed a large grid of simulations that span a reasonable amount of the parameter space that may described the initial conditions of the Hyades star cluster, comparing final-day mass profile and morphology of the simulated streams with those of the observed stream to conclude that the Hyades’ progenitor cluster likely had an initial mass of between $1400\text{--}1600 M_{\odot}$ and an initial half-mass radius of between $4\text{--}6$ pc. We found the initial position and velocity vectors of the cluster that would have resulted in its current-day position and velocity for all simulations in the parameter space, and we observed the effects of varying the mass and half-mass radius of the initial cluster on the final-day mass profile and morphology. We also performed additional tests to observe the impact of the external dark matter halo in the evolution of the star cluster.

1. Introduction

The Hyades cluster is one of the closest stellar clusters to the Earth and is an important target for studies of galactic and stellar evolution. The cluster has an estimated age of 625 ± 50 Myr, some 300 members, and a total mass of $300\text{--}400 M_{\odot}$, sitting at a distance of ~ 46 pc from Earth (Perryman et al. 1998).

Recent kinematic data from the GAIA telescope has provided more accurate datasets for the stars in the Hyades cluster, constrained the member stars in the cluster, and provided clear evidence for the presence of large-scale “tidal tails”, or stellar streams — the first for a cluster bound to the Milky Way galactic disk (Meingast & Alves, 2018). These streams are characterized by a flattened, S-shaped structure of stars parallel to the plane of the galactic disk with a distinct, dense center and extended tails (shown in Figure 1).

Figure 1: Morphology of the Hyades stellar streams in the present day. Figure reproduced from Meingast & Alves (2018).

The characteristic structure of these stellar streams make them a strong candidate for probing the evolution of the galactic dark matter halo through observation of the tidal forces on the stars in the Hyades cluster, and indeed, the formation of the streams by gravitational forces has been predicted and previously studied through numerical simulation (Ernst et al. 2011, see also references therein). This study is similar to previous studies in its methods and focus but makes use of more recent observational data for the Hyades (Meingast & Alves 2018) as well as a dynamic model for the dark matter halo developed by Bose et al. (2018) to determine the properties of the progenitor cluster to the Hyades and to observe the effects of the dark matter halo on the development of stellar stream structures.

2. Numerical Methods

2.1. Galactic gravitational potential and tidal background

The gravitational potential of the host galaxy in this simulation was of particular importance, as it is the largest determining factor in the final-day morphology of a simulated tidal stream. We considered a gravitational potential with a smooth dark matter halo component of a Milky Way-like galaxy and a central disk galaxy component. This potential was modeled following the procedure outlined in Bose et al. (2018) with the following characteristics.

The dark matter halo component of the gravitational potential was drawn from dark matter simulations (Bose et al. 2016, Hellwing et al. 2016) for a halo with $M_{200} = 1.5 \times 10^{12} M_{\odot}$ where M_{200} is the mass contained within which the mean density is 200 times the critical density of the universe. This potential varies with redshift and radius and co-evolves with the cluster over time in the simulation.

The central galactic disk component of the gravitational potential was modeled as the superposition of three Miyamoto-Nagai disk potentials (Miyamoto & Nagai 1975), as described by Smith et al. (2015) and modeled after a Milky Way disk with a scale length of 3 kpc, scale height of 300 pc, and a total mass of $5 \times 10^{10} M_{\odot}$.

The gravitational potential described here was integrated into our simulation software so that in addition to the gravitational interactions between stars in the cluster, each star was also influenced by the gravitational “tides” of the surrounding galaxy.

2.2. MCLUSTER code for generation initial conditions

Initial conditions for these simulations was generated using the MCLUSTER code (Küpper et al., 2011) with set parameters as outlined in Table 1. While the half-mass radius and total mass of the cluster was varied across simulations, all initial clusters were created according to a King density profile with a W_0 value of 6.0, indicating a moderate concentration (King, 1966). Additionally, the initial mass function was defined by Kroupa (2001) with optimal sampling. Bounds were placed on the masses of included stars in the cluster, with a lower limit of $0.05 M_{\odot}$ and upper limit of $100 M_{\odot}$. This study excluded primordial binary systems from initial conditions.

Table 1: MCLUSTER command line parameters used to generate cluster models

<u>Option</u>	<u>Meaning</u>	<u>Chosen value</u>	<u>Value Significance</u>
-M	Total mass of initial cluster	[<i>Variable</i>]	--
-P	Density profile	[1]	King (1966) density profile
-W	W_0 for King model	[6]	W_0 (dimensionless parameter) for King profile
-R	Half-mass radius (pc)	[<i>Variable</i>]	--
-T	Computational time in NBODY units	[100]	Temporary value, changed later in NBODY input file
-Q	Virial ratio	[0.5]	$Q = 0.5$ for virial equilibrium
-o	Output name of cluster model	[<i>name</i>]	Output name (changes by test)
-f	Initial mass function	[3]	Kroupa (2001) with optimal sampling IMF
-m -m	IMF mass limits (lower and upper bounds, respectively) in M_\odot	[0.05][100]	Places lower limit of $0.05 M_\odot$ and upper limit of $100 M_\odot$ on stars in cluster
-b	Binary fraction	[0]	Produces cluster without binary systems
-s	Random number seed	[71799]	Random number seed for NBODY code; same number used across all simulations
-t	Tidal field	[3]	Temporary value, changed later in NBODY input file according to Bose et al. (2018) potential
-X -X -X	Galactocentric position vector of cluster center (X, Y, Z) (kpc)	[-8.04] [0] [0]	Present-day position of the Hyades cluster center
-V -V -V	Galactocentric velocity vector of cluster center (X, Y, Z) (km/s)	[+30.1] [+202.9] [-6.0]	Present-day velocity of the Hyades cluster center with signs flipped
-u	Output units (NBODY/astrophysical)	[1]	Output in astrophysical units
-C	Output type	[5]	NBODY6++-compatible output files

2.3. Use of NBODY6++ for simulating gravitational interactions

This study makes use of the publicly available NBODY6++ code, recently updated in August 2019 and outlined by Khalisi et al. (2019), to compute the point-by-point gravitational interactions and the influence of tidal forces on the stars contained in the cluster using Newtonian equations of motion. The NBODY code also has the added benefit of providing a model for stellar evolution and its effects on the distribution and interaction of stars in the cluster. The simulations reported in this study were all initialized using the same random number seed and evolved for a simulation time of 625 Myr, based on the lifetime of the Hyades reported in Perryman et al. (1998). Simulations were run on the supercomputer at the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics located in Cambridge, MA.

2.4. Varying of initial conditions

The initial conditions varied in this study, as alluded to in Table 1, are the initial total mass and the half-mass radius of the progenitor cluster. The grid of simulations performed span a reasonable range of initial mass and half-mass radius values; this parameter space and the naming conventions used to distinguish each simulation are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Grid of initial conditions parameters and naming conventions (*italicized*)

	Mass = 1000 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1200 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1400 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1600 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1800 M_{\odot}
R = 2 pc	<i>M1000R2</i>	<i>M1200R2</i>	<i>M1400R2</i>	<i>M1600R2</i>	<i>M1800R2</i>
R = 4 pc	<i>M1000R4</i>	<i>M1200R4</i>	<i>M1400R4</i>	<i>M1600R4</i>	<i>M1800R4</i>
R = 6 pc	<i>M1000R6</i>	<i>M1200R6</i>	<i>M1400R6</i>	<i>M1600R6</i>	<i>M1800R6</i>
R = 8 pc	<i>M1000R8</i>	<i>M1200R8</i>	<i>M1400R8</i>	<i>M1600R8</i>	<i>M1800R8</i>

A sample of initial mass profiles (mass contained as a function of radius) are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Initial mass profiles of several progenitor clusters. The mass profiles follow a King (1966) profile prior to their evolution in the simulation.

Increasing the total mass of the initial cluster will, in general, increase the mass contained within small radii in the final-day cluster structure, though through its evolution the simulated clusters will lose significant mass to the gravitational tides of the galaxy. The effect of the half-mass radius on the final-day morphology and mass profile is a bit more subtle, but clusters with a larger initial half-mass radius are less dense and will be pulled farther apart than more dense clusters with more mass in their centers.

2.5. Defining cluster centers

Over the course of the cluster’s evolution, the cluster becomes less dense and individual stars drift away from the main structure in the cluster. The stellar stream structure in the final-day snapshot contains only a fraction of the original stars in the cluster, as others may have

drifted in other directions or been stripped from the central structure. Thus, the center of mass of all stars in the simulation no longer defines a meaningful origin of points, and it is necessary to define a standard algorithm for finding the center of the final-day structure.

The algorithm we used consisted of the following steps: first, the center of mass was computed, and a sphere centered on that point and with the farthest star on its surface was defined. The sphere is then shrunk by 5%, ignoring the stars far from the center of mass, and a new center of mass is computed. This procedure is repeated until 1% of the original stars are contained in the sphere, and center of mass of the remaining stars is taken to be the new center of the structure. This process not only standardizes the defined center of a heterogeneous distribution of stars but, qualitatively, also finds the center of the densest region of stars.

2.6. Determining initial galactocentric position and velocity vectors

To ensure that the final-day cluster is located in the same place as the present-day Hyades, the NBODY simulations were each run twice; the first time, to determine where the progenitor cluster must have started in order to end up at the measured position and velocity coordinates of the Hyades today; the second time, to actually simulate the evolution of the cluster.

The cluster was initialized as indicated earlier using the MCLUSTER code, with the position vector and the negative of the velocity vector of the present-day Hyades. When input into NBODY, the initial push of the velocity vector sets the cluster in orbit in reverse, starting from the current position of the Hyades and evolving over 625 Myr. The final-day velocity and position vectors of this first simulation are then input (again reversing the sign of the velocity vector) as the initial vectors in the second simulation, again with the initial cluster, and evolved for 625 Myr to end at the present-day position and velocity of the Hyades. The determined initial position and velocity vectors are summarized in Table A in the appendices at the end of this paper.

3. Results

For the grid of simulations outlined in Table 2, each simulation produced several pieces of data, including a final-day mass profile from the computed center, a plot of the final-day morphology of the stream, and tracking of the cluster’s orbit over the 625 Myr of evolution. Each of these is discussed below, with excerpted plots to illustrate the diversity of mass profiles and morphologies produced by this study’s simulations. Additionally, the simulated plots for each dataset is compared against GAIA DR2 data as reported previously by Meingast & Alves (2018).

3.1. Final-day mass profiles

Comparing the final-day mass profiles of different progenitor clusters in the parameter space is a good first measure for finding the “best fit” progenitor model to the Hyades cluster that we see today and therefore making a prediction about the initial mass and half-mass radius of the progenitor cluster.

The current-day mass profile of the Hyades cluster was extracted from GAIA DR2 data and is shown in all mass profile graphs as a dotted line. The data shows the mass profile of the present-day cluster containing a total mass of $448.76 M_{\odot}$ within 29.27 pc of the cluster center.

By observing the mass profile plots of different simulations in the parameter space, we can also make qualitative assessments about how changing the initial conditions will change the final-day distribution of mass in the cluster. In Figure 3, the mass profile curves for progenitors of initial mass $M = 1000 M_{\odot}$ are shown. For simulations with a larger initial half-light radius and therefore a more diffuse initial cluster, the final-day cluster contains less mass within 30 pc as stars are more easily stripped away by the gravitational tides over its evolution. Conversely, simulations with a smaller half-light radius are more densely packed and better retain their compact cores, resulting in more mass concentrated towards their center in the final day.

Figure 3: Final-day mass profiles of simulations with initial mass of $M = 1000 M_{\odot}$.

A chi-squared analysis was performed to quantify which simulated mass profiles best fit the actual data (shown in Table 3). The best-fitting mass profiles were that of a progenitor cluster with total initial mass = $1200 M_{\odot}$ and half-mass radius of 4 pc and a cluster with total initial mass = $1400 M_{\odot}$ and a half-mass radius of 6 pc (highlighted in pink) while the other mass profiles that appeared close to the observational data are highlighted in yellow.

Table 3: Chi Squared Values for mass profile fit with observational data

	M1000	M1200	M1400	M1600	M1800
R2	922.39	1241.96	8092.14	12804.73	23248.12
R4	150.54	142.50	3256.00	3711.47	10245.59
R6	1484.08	3276.37	143.07	224.70	1752.00
R8	4132.05	7647.87	2872.69	4764.12	229.45

The mass profiles of the simulations with the lowest chi squared value (and thus the best fit with observational data) are shown in Figure 4. The computed mass profiles for all simulations can be found in Appendix B.

Figure 4: Final-day mass profiles of simulations with lowest chi squared value. This can be contrasted with Figure 2, which shows the initial mass profiles of the same simulated cluster before evolution.

3.2. Final-day morphology

From the different initial conditions, simulations produced a wide variety of final-day cluster morphologies; however, all simulations have predicted the formation of stellar structures consistent with the characteristic flattened S-shape, dense center, and curled tails as reported in Meingast & Alves (2018) and shown in Figure 1.

These simulations demonstrate strong evidence that stellar streams similar to those observed by GAIA DR2 will form in a stellar cluster as the result of gravitational interactions and stellar evolution modeled in the NBODY6++ code, regardless of initial conditions. Figures 5–6 show a sample of the diversity of morphologies produced by different simulations in the parameter space by plotting the X-Y and X-Z positions of the stars in the final-day cluster and comparing them to the observational data from GAIA DR2. These plots are in galactocentric coordinates, taking the X-Y plane to be parallel to the plane of the central disk galaxy. The full plots of the stars in each simulation can be found in Appendix C.

Figure 5: Final-day morphologies of simulated clusters (blue) compared with observational data (black) at one initial total mass ($M=1200 M_{\odot}$) and varying initial half-mass radius.

Figure 6: Final-day morphologies of simulated clusters (blue) compared with observational data (black) at one initial half-mass radius (4 pc) and varying initial total mass.

From the chi squared analysis of the mass profiles describe in section 3.1, five simulations in the parameter space were chosen as the closest possible fits (shown in Table 3) based on their final-day mass profile. The morphologies of those five simulations are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Final-day morphologies of simulated clusters (blue) compared with observational data (black) of the best-fit simulations to the observational data, based on mass profile..

A common discrepancy between all simulations and the observed data is the axis of rotational symmetry of the S-shape in the stellar stream, a result which is discussed in Appendix D. This might suggest a difference in how the origin of coordinates are defined in the simulation data versus the observational data, but adjusting the simulations to match the rotational symmetry of the observational data is beyond the scope of this thesis.

3.3. Orbit of cluster in galactocentric coordinates

As discussed previously, the orbit of the cluster around the galaxy is of particular interest because if proper initial position velocity vectors are chosen, the cluster should evolve while orbiting the galactic plane and end up at its current observed position after 625 Myr. Using the method introduced previously, these initial vectors were found, and in all cases the final-day position of the cluster fell within ± 0.13 kpc in any direction of the intended position (Appendix E). An example orbit of a simulated cluster ($M = 1400 M_{\odot}$ and $R = 6$ pc) is shown in Figure 8 below to illustrate the typical path of the cluster around the galaxy.

Figure 8: 2-D and 3-D orbits of a cluster around the galaxy, in galactocentric coordinates. The blue cross on all diagrams indicates the starting position of the cluster.

3.4. Evolution of a cluster in the absence of the dark matter halo potential

This study also aimed to investigate the effect of the dark matter halo potential alone on the evolution of a stellar cluster. As described above, all of the regular simulations in this study were done in a gravitational potential with both a disk and halo component, but it was also of interest to determine the effect of the dynamic halo model against a simulation containing only the static potential of the Milky Way disk. Therefore, an additional simulation of one cluster in the parameter space was run following all of the above procedures, but with the contribution of the dark matter halo “turned off” in the gravitational potential, in order to quantify the contribution of the halo in the cluster’s evolution.

A cluster with an initial mass of $M = 1400 M_{\odot}$ and half-light radius of $R = 6$ pc was chosen as the test cluster in the “no-halo” simulation. Following earlier naming conventions, the “no-halo” simulation is indicated by “NHM1400R6” in the following figures.

The mass profile of the “halo-off” simulation compared with the “halo-on” simulation with identical initial conditions is shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Final-day mass profiles of no-halo simulation of M1400R6 cluster (orange line) compared with the original M1400R6 cluster (blue line) and observational data (black dotted line).

The morphology plots of these two simulations are shown below, in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Final-day morphologies of no-halo simulation compared to original simulation and observational data.

Finally, the orbits of the cluster in both simulations are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: 2-D orbit of cluster in no-halo simulation and original (with-halo) simulation around the galaxy, in galactocentric coordinates. The crosses on indicate the starting position of the clusters.

Comparing the simulation with the dark matter halo potential turned on and the simulation with it turned off demonstrates the significance of the halo effect on the final-day mass profile and morphology of the cluster as well as the effect that it has on the implied initial position and velocity vectors of the cluster. In the no-halo simulation, the cluster orbits farther from the center of the galaxy and is subject to weaker gravitational tides throughout its evolution; as a result, the stars in the cluster are able to stay closely bound to each other and less mass is stripped away, as shown by both the mass profile and morphology plots.

This comparison is also valuable in showing the importance of the environment that the cluster evolves in and the impact of changes in the tidal background on the morphology and properties of the final-day stellar structure. It demonstrates also how these stellar structures can be used in future work to further probe the features of the galactic environment that they evolved in.

4. Conclusions

In this study we have reported the results of simulations to model the formation of stellar streams from a globular cluster in the tidal forces of the combined Milky Way disk and halo potential. We observed directly the effects of changing the initial mass and half-mass radius of a progenitor cluster on the final-day mass profile and morphology of a cluster after 625 Myr of evolution in a gravitational background. We found that stellar stream structures were indeed produced from a model of stellar evolution and the gravitational interactions between stars and the potential of the host galaxy, and that our final-day clusters reasonably matched the observed Hyades stream in mass profile and morphology across almost all simulations in our parameter space in that the characteristic shape of a tidal tail was consistently produced, though its specific morphology is sensitive to differing initial conditions.

Across the grid of simulations, we used chi squared to make a measure of how closely the simulated stream matched the observational data; a summary of the results is shown in Table 4 below. The simulations that best fit the observed data are shown in the lightest blue.

Table 4: Summary of goodness of fit with observational data for simulations in parameter space, denoted by color (key below).

	Mass = 1000 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1200 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1400 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1600 M_{\odot}	Mass = 1800 M_{\odot}
R = 2 pc	<i>M1000R2</i>	<i>M1200R2</i>	<i>M1400R2</i>	<i>M1600R2</i>	<i>M1800R2</i>
R = 4 pc	<i>M1000R4</i>	<i>M1200R4</i>	<i>M1400R4</i>	<i>M1600R4</i>	<i>M1800R4</i>
R = 6 pc	<i>M1000R6</i>	<i>M1200R6</i>	<i>M1400R6</i>	<i>M1600R6</i>	<i>M1800R6</i>
R = 8 pc	<i>M1000R8</i>	<i>M1200R8</i>	<i>M1400R8</i>	<i>M1600R8</i>	<i>M1800R8</i>

Very bad fit	Bad fit	Moderate fit	Good fit	Best fit
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Additionally, we performed an extra simulation to show the effect of the dark matter halo model on the evolution of the cluster and demonstrated the sensitivity of these structures to the environment in which they evolve.

As with any simulation-based study, there are many complicated physical processes and structures that have been excluded from these simulations in order to balance physical realism with computational efficiency. In reality, many other physical and cosmological processes are at play in the evolution of a cluster in the galaxy, and future studies may consider effects that we have excluded or answer questions which are outside the scope of this study.

As previously discussed, a limitation of this work was the assumption of a static, stationary central galactic disk potential, and as a result the effects dynamical friction are thus not included in the evolution of the clusters in this system. Because the age and evolution time of the cluster in this study is only 625 Myr, rather than the typical lifetime of a globular cluster (on the order of 10^9 years), the effect of these features on the evolution of the Hyades may be less dramatic than on older clusters but may still merit further study in future works. Another limitation of the disk galaxy potential used in this study was that it modeled the bulge and thin and thick disks without taking into account the effects of spiral arms that are characteristic of the Milky Way galaxy and which may have had a significant effect on stellar clusters passing through them. Simulations of objects in our galaxy such as those reported here may be refined and revisited as detailed models for the galactic disk potential become available.

Other factors on cluster evolution that were outside the scope of this study, such as the inclusion of primordial binary systems, different models of the dark matter halo potential, or other astrophysical effects as they emerge from future observational data, may also be integrated into these simulations in future studies to paint a more complete picture of the evolution of clusters over time. As more abundant and accurate data becomes available from GAIA and others, these studies may be extended to simulate the formation of other stellar streams and phenomena.

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Appendices:

Appendix A: Table of position and velocity vectors for each set of initial conditions

		M1000	M1200	M1400	M1600	M1800
R2	x, y, z	-6.9 -7.75 -0.01	-6.72 -7.83 -0.02	-6.69 -7.85 -0.02	-6.93 -7.73 -0.01	-6.77 -7.81 -0.02
	v _x , v _y , v _z	-145.0 73.7 4.9	-147.3 71.0 4.9	-147.7 70.5 4.9	-144.6 74.1 4.9	-146.7 71.7 4.9
R4	x, y, z	-6.74 -7.82 -0.02	-6.29 -8.03 -0.03	-7.24 -7.56 0.0	-6.48 -7.95 -0.02	-6.95 -7.72 -0.01
	v _x , v _y , v _z	-147.0 71.3 4.9	-152.6 64.6 4.7	-140.4 78.6 4.9	-150.3 67.4 4.8	-144.3 74.4 4.9
R6	x, y, z	-7.68 -7.3 0.02	-5.44 -8.35 -0.05	-5.81 -8.22 -0.04	-5.6 -8.29 -0.05	-6.95 -7.72 -0.01
	v _x , v _y , v _z	-134.2 84.8 4.9	-161.9 51.5 4.1	-157.9 57.4 4.4	-160.2 54.0 4.2	-144.3 74.4 4.9
R8	x, y, z	-5.76 -8.24 -0.05	-5.05 -8.46 -0.06	-5.68 -8.26 -0.05	-6.94 -7.73 -0.01	-7.18 -7.6 -0.0
	v _x , v _y , v _z	-158.5 56.6 4.4	-165.7 45.4 3.7	-159.4 55.3 4.3	-144.6 74.1 4.9	-141.2 77.7 4.9

No halo		M1400
R6	x, y, z	-7.92 4.23 -0.09
	v _x , v _y , v _z	33.4 188.1 1.5

Appendix B: Full mass profiles for simulated clusters in the final day, compared with observational data and sorted by mass

Mass profile (R-M) Hyades Data and M1200 Sim Data

Mass profiles for initial mass = 1200 M_{\odot}

Mass profile (R-M) Hyades Data and M1400 Sim Data

Mass profiles for initial mass = 1400 M_{\odot}

Mass profile (R-M) Hyades Data and M1600 Sim Data

Mass profiles for initial mass = 1600 M_{\odot}

Mass profile (R-M) Hyades Data and M1800 Sim Data

Mass profiles for initial mass = 1800 M_{\odot}

All simulation data final-day mass profiles

Appendix C: Full morphology plots for simulated clusters in the final day, compared with observational data and sorted by mass

Position plots for initial mass = $1000 M_{\odot}$

Position plots for initial mass = $1200 M_{\odot}$

Position plots for initial mass = $1400 M_{\odot}$

Appendix D: Discussion of rotational position of final-day clusters

As discussed in section 3.2, the morphologies of the simulated clusters have a different rotational symmetry than the observed data, even though the structures look very similar. To probe the possibility that some definition of the axes was the cause of the different in symmetry, a simulation was run on the M1400R6 simulation with a different origin of coordinates is defined

(by flipping the signs of the final-day velocity vector). The results of that simulation are shown below (with this experimental simulation named “New M1400R6”):

The orbit figure here demonstrates the purpose of this test, which was to have the M1400R6 cluster end up in the correct final-day position but with the opposite velocity vectors. The initial position and velocity vectors for the cluster center has also been adjusted accordingly.

The mass profile figure reflects that because the cluster took a different path during its evolution, the final-day mass profile was different than that of an identical cluster. The computed chi squared value for this new simulation was also 80, significantly lower than the lowest chi squared value from the regular grid of simulations reported in this study (142) and therefore might necessitate a reassessment of best-fit simulations in a future work.

The morphology of this new simulation is of greatest interest, because although it does not exhibit the characteristic S-shape of the stellar streams discussed in this study, the axis of rotational symmetry has noticeably shifted, suggesting that some coordinate transformation may solve the discrepancy in the main grid of simulations we have performed.

Appendix E: Final-day position and velocity vectors of cluster center

Simulation name	Final-day position vector	Final-day velocity vector
M1000R2	-8.04 0.06 0.0	-31.2 -202.9 6.0
M1000R4	-8.05 -0.13 0.01	-27.7 -202.9 6.1
M1000R6	-8.04 -0.03 0.0	-29.8 -202.9 6.0
M1000R8	-8.04 0.04 0.0	-30.8 -202.9 6.1
M1200R2	-8.05 -0.09 0.0	-28.4 -202.9 6.1
M1200R4	-8.04 0.03 0.0	-30.6 -202.9 6.0
M1200R6	-8.03 0.07 0.0	-31.5 -203.0 5.8
M1200R8	-8.04 -0.02 0.0	-29.8 -203.0 5.8
M1400R2	-8.04 -0.02 0.0	-29.7 -202.9 6.1
M1400R4	-8.05 -0.1 0.0	-28.4 -202.9 6.0
M1400R6	-8.05 -0.04 0.0	-29.3 -202.9 5.8
M1400R8	-8.05 -0.06 0.0	-29.0 -202.9 6.0
M1600R2	-8.04 -0.03 0.0	-29.6 -202.9 6.0
M1600R4	-8.04 0.02 -0.0	-30.5 -202.9 5.9
M1600R6	-8.05 -0.08 0.0	-28.6 -202.9 5.9
M1600R8	-8.03 0.08 -0.0	-31.7 -203.0 6.0

M1800R2	-8.04 -0.02 0.0	-29.8 -202.9 6.1
M1800R4	-8.05 -0.05 0.0	-29.1 -202.9 6.0
M1800R6	-8.05 -0.05 0.0	-29.2 -202.9 6.0
M1800R8	-8.04 -0.05 0.0	-29.1 -202.9 5.9